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Title:

**Does the Recent Growth of Wine Business Affect
Hospitality Graduating Students' Intention to be a
Sommelier?**

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Executive Summary

This dissertation aims to realize hospitality graduating students' intentions of developing their future career as sommeliers based on the growing Asian wine market. Barron (2008) and Littlejohn and Watson (2004), described the hospitality graduate's intention, explore how to attract the student attaching or join the hospitality industry upon graduation. However, this report further studies the graduating student's intention, it is focused on examining the attractiveness of sommelier's career for hospitality graduating students and hopes the results can provide useful insights for practitioners' consideration.

The literature review is emphasized on five parts, which includes the factors affecting student choose sommelier, the definition of sommelier in this report, wine business situation, the condition and the hospitality graduating student's intention. Literature review proved the recent growth of wine business is affecting sommelier demand, and the market is growing.

The research is via a questionnaire that to find the result of this study. Regarding the data collection, the total has 118 questionnaires were collected, all respondents were the student who are studying the hospitality, which includes 78 higher diploma students and 40 bachelor's degree students.

In finding, the result found out the main factors affecting the hospitality graduating students' intention to be a sommelier is interest, job content and salary. However, per five hospitality students only four understand sommelier's key responsibilities. Also, per ten students only two or three students want to be a sommelier, the situation is worse.

Finally, the report recommended 3 "E". First, "Enhancing" the frequency of sommelier education; Second, "Encourage" industry to study sommelier; Third, "Enhancing" the sommelier reputation. Those suggestion based on the result to the identification, the purpose is improving student's intention to be a sommelier.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Research Background

In recent years, wine consumption is much more common than before. It isn't just consumed by specialist or wealthy people only, it becomes more popular in the world markets, particularly in Asia (Ritchie, 2009).

4 As shown in Table 1, the Mainland China's wine imports have kept growing since 2008, with an increase of USD 593 million in nine year time, representing a 315 per cent increase when compared to that of 2008. Moreover, the Hong Kong wine market has also experienced a growth of Asian wine market, the Asian wine imports increased by nearly four times, with an average increase of HK\$587 million per year between 2007 and 2017 (see Table 2). Those tables demonstrated that Asia especially Hong Kong's wine market is growing.

Therefore, the Asian markets need some wine experts such as 'Sommelier' to select and serve quality wine to the growing demands, and that is the potential future (Lee, 2017). This research focuses on examining whether the increasing wine market will attract hospitality graduating students to develop their career as a sommelier upon graduation.

In Hong Kong, many hospitality institutes have provided wine and spirit courses, and wine service courses for students, such as the Hong Kong International Culinary Institute (ICI) offers the Higher Diploma in Wine and Beverage Business Management (VTC, 2018). And the additional certifications like 'Count of Master Sommelier' and Wine and Spirit Education Trust (WSET) are more popular, and this may enhance the graduating student's success rate for applying the sommelier job (Puckette, 2014).

Since the appearance of first China's 'Master Sommelier', the sommelier becomes a career star in the Asian hospitality industry especially in China, Taiwan and Hong Kong (Binkiewicz, 2017). The reason that I choose this topic is mainly due to the growing wine market in recent years, which is the globalization of trade. How many hospitality students intend to be a sommelier and motivated by the wine market trend or they comprehend the fact of the market, but they don't have any motivation and action.

Barron (2008), and Littlejohn and Watson (2004), described the hospitality graduate's direction, intention and job expectation, explore how to attract the students attaching or joining the hospitality industry upon graduation. Those are the most critical resources to recognise the hospitality graduate's direction and intention, but not just focused on the Sommelier. Furthermore, Schoffstall (2013) described the relationship between work and study, but the most information demonstrates the Western countries' situation rather than the Asian countries. Also, Manske and Cordua (2005) described the efficiency and effectiveness of sommelier and indicating the market demand for the sommelier. But it isn't related to hospitality graduate's intention. Thus, ³⁹ this paper aims to fill this gap by exploring the hospitality graduate's intention and investigate whether they want to be a sommelier, especially in China and Hong Kong which are rarely discussed in the previous study.

Table 1: Growth of wine imports in Mainland China from 2008 to 2017

(Source: HKTDC Research, 2008)

Table 2: Growth of Asian Wine Imports through Hong Kong from 2007 to 2017

(Source: HKTDC Research, 2008)

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1.2 Aim of the Study

This research aims to realise hospitality graduating students' intentions of developing their future career as sommeliers based on the growing Asian wine market. It focuses on examining the attractiveness of sommelier's career for hospitality graduating students and hopes the results can provide useful insights for practitioners' consideration.

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1.3 Objectives of the Study

To meet the above aim, the objectives of this study are set below:

1. To identify the key attributes affecting hospitality graduating students' career intentions.
2. To investigate students' major concerns for developing future career as a sommelier factors.
3. To analyse student's intention to develop future career as a sommelier.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Graduating student's Intention and Industry Situation

In few years, Hong Kong most hospitality graduating student doesn't ⁶⁵ want to work in the hospitality industry especially food and beverage department, they want to change the career aspect (McMahon and Quinn, 1995). Also, salary, job expectation, work life balance and opportunity are some common factors affecting hospitality graduates' career intentions (Blomme, Rheede and Tromp, 2013). Besides, the working hours and unstable working period also affect students' intentions ² to develop their future career in the hospitality industry after graduation (Schoffstall, 2013).

In general, the hospitality student's intention only has four choices. One is never planning to ³⁹ work in the hospitality industry; one is work in the hospitality industry but not the 'Food and Beverage' department, one is they are work in 'Food and Beverage' industry. The final choice is working in hospitality industry also intend 'Food and Beverage' department and sommelier. This research mainly focuses on the third and final choices when they after graduated. These two assumptions can demonstrate the pros and cons of being a sommelier, also recognise the important factors of sommelier attraction, related benefit and the student intention with a sommelier. It is hoped that this study can find the key elements of the hospitality graduates' intention.

According to the recent report of VTC (2016), the manpower ⁸ in the hospitality industry and the graduating student situation. In Table 3 shows manpower of the catering industry was kept increasing from 2005 to 2011, but 2011 to 2015 was relatively stable with 180,000

employees. And Table 4 shows the beverage serving employees which includes bartender and sommelier representing 4 per cent of the F&B employees, around 7,583 employees worked in Hong Kong. These data help to illustrate the manpower in catering is stable, but the professional beverage talent job holds 4 per cent although beverage related position can also be available for the 41 per cent for Non-Chinese restaurants duty and 8 per cent for event catering, the demand of beverage expert especially sommelier is less. Furthermore, the hospitality school program is increasing such as International Culinary Institute and Hotel and Tourism Institute (VTC, 2016). That means most hospitality graduates seldom work in the industry in these few years especially beverage server. The catering industry should enhance the manpower and service quality ² to maintain Hong Kong's reputation as the "Culinary Capital of Asia".

Table 3: Trend of Manpower 2005 - 2015

(Source: Catering Industry Manpower Survey Report, 2015)

Table 4: Distribution of Employees by Branch

(Source: Catering Industry Manpower Survey Report, 2015)

2.2 Definition of Sommelier

According to Cambridge Dictionary, the term Sommelier means someone whose job is to serve and give advice about wine in a restaurant (Cambridge Dictionary, 2018). W.F.com (2018, para. 1) indicated that “A Sommelier is a certified wine professional trained in tasting and pairing wines. They have an intimate knowledge of wine terms, regions, characteristics and tastings”. Green (2003) described a sommelier “is skilled in the art of matching wine with food to augment the food's flavour. With their specialised training and fine-tuned palates, sommeliers serve as restaurants' wine experts and share this expertise with restaurant guests”. (p. 30).

Regarding the qualification, to become a sommelier requires an extended period of learning, also it needs many tasting experiences to maintain the professional skill and image (Lee, 2017). The job requirements of sommelier require lots of knowledge about beverages and manage the bar even serve the cigar, not just serve wine and work with fine dining restaurant

(Puckette, 2014). However, the sommelier can be defined to a wine steward, which is the wine and cellar manager and specialist (Manske and Cordua, 2005). Also, most hospitality trainees have service knowledge but lack of practice (Baum, 1991). Therefore, fresh hospitality graduates with a WSET certification is not enough to become a sommelier, they need more practical experience. For example, ÉPURE in Hong Kong requested the sommelier to possess a minimum five years' relevant experience in luxury hotels or western fine dining restaurants (JobsDB, 2018). But the student can step by step to increase the experience and become a sommelier.

Generally, the sommelier beverage knowledge is diverse, not just wine, and it involved any beverage like sake, cocktail, tea. However, this study mainly focuses on the wine sommelier in the hospitality industry.

2.3 Situation of Wine Business

The wine business is growing in Asia. The wine market in China will overtake the UK as the world's second-largest market for wine by 2020 although the domestic brands have 80 per cent, and China just behind Spain, it already becomes the world's second-largest wine production country (Krich, 2018). However, China ⁴³ per capita volume of wine consumption is only 6 per cent of the world's average (Jenster and Cheng, 2008). So, that is the incredible potential market. Furthermore, Hong Kong and Asia Pacific region are continuing to maintain a significant business hub, forecasted regional growth over the next five years from \$29 billion in 2016 to \$40.8 billion by 2021 and Chinese consumption is expected to rise by over one-third to \$23 billion when it reaches volume of 192 million cases for the next five years (Wang, 2018).

In Hong Kong, ²⁰ since 2008, the government removed all duty-related customs and administrative controls for wine, which can enhance the Hong Kong international wine business situation and trade with Mainland China. Chan (2017b) stated that ²⁵ "Hong Kong has entered into an agreement with the mainland Chinese Government, allowing wine imports to go into China under CEPA and enhanced customs facilitation measures".

According to the Hong Kong Trade Development Council's (HKTDC) research, the wine-related business includes ⁴⁴ auction, retailing, warehousing, catering and transportation. Around 850 new wine-related companies were set up in Hong Kong between 2008 and 2009, total around 3,550 (Chan, 2017a). Mr. Guillaume Deglise, CEO of Vinexpo, stated that: "Being in Hong Kong since 1998 is a winning strategic choice that Vinexpo offers to its

clients” (Wang, 2018, para. 11). The extensive wine event ‘Vinexpo’ often hold in Hong Kong, it indicates the wine business is growing.

Many European noticed that Asia, for example, due to the same culture of sharing plates and dining together, Alejandro Garcia Lopez who is the famous Spanish winemaker, he designed a wine to suit the shared dining experience in Asia (Raguraman, 2018). This could demonstrate the Asian wine business and market help to attract business from Europe. Also, Canada in connection with the Asian market, it provided a new wine promotion (Mirror, 2018). Thus, the wine education and wine consultant are necessary especially for the Mainland

2.4 The Condition of Graduating Students' Intention

First is regarding the current trend, based on the career path and learning aspects, hospitality graduating student may choose the smaller firm like Marco Polo which can comprehensive to learn the hotel operation due to the inadequate manpower (Jameson and Holden, 2000). Also, the student's transcript or performance appraisal may affect their career intention for other industry or entrepreneurship when they enter the labour market, the education and transcripts are affecting the graduates' intention (Mohamad, Lim, Yusof and Soon, 2015). However, the career path is narrow, for example, the ² survey reveals that in September 2015, a total of 182,526 persons were employed in the catering industry, only 4.7% were in the managerial category, less than 5% employees can become the managerial role (VTC, 2016). It shows the promotion and career path are narrow which affect the fresh graduate's student intend to work in the industry.

Second is regarding the salary and work content, most hospitality students feel negative for the salary, and they think the promotion of hospitality is limit, the vast gap between expectation and realisation discourage many ⁷⁴ students do intend to work in the hospitality industry (Blomme et al., 2013). Studying hospitality and working in the hospitality industry are two different things, the salary and work content are the key concerns for hospitality graduates to develop future career. And based on those elements, most hospitality graduating students' expectation level is decreasing when they are studying, it is because they found the salary and work content were quite different from their expectation during the internship training (Lu and Adler, 2009).

For the challenging in hospitality industry, the primary challenge is how to retain the high-educated staff especially the degree student, also the industry needs to focus on how to avoid the hospitality graduates job changing (Hoque, 1999). Most hospitality graduates left because of the compensation and working hours, most hospitality firm like hotels haven't noted that problem, during the internship, very rush and long hour mentality even lousy attitude to treat the graduating student, that may let them have a negative impact on this industry and never return (Brown, Thomas and Bosselman, 2015). In Hong Kong, most non-supervisory employees' commitment is shallow, and the turnover rate is high (Wong, 1991). Also, hospitality graduates will become the newcomers who influence the latter's turnover and commitment. Training and job consultation are the suitable solutions for retaining staff and decrease the turnover rate (Lam, Lo and Chan, 2002).

Regarding the solution, the work-based learning can let the graduates early to recognise the situation of hospitality job (Littlejohn and Watson, 2004). However, most hospitality internship, the employer didn't consider the student status to design the training program and job content, most internships was lack of quality and diversified due to the employer was short of concern, it let many students abandon or change another career aspect after undergoing their internship (Lee and Chao, 2013).

2.5 Factors Affecting Student Choose Sommelier

Limitation and Chance of Sommelier

In Hong Kong, being the member of *Hong Kong Sommelier Association* (HKSA) is the best choice for developing the business of sommelier. Since 1997, the association started to arrange their sommelier competition, but the requirement requests the participator was having numerous experiences and became a member (HKSA, 2017). Thus, it limits hospitality graduating students who are fewer experiences to join the association, and the difficulty affects the graduating students develop the career path as a sommelier.

Furthermore, most international wine certification need to spend a lot of money, according to Table 5, the famous wine international education and training certification *Wine and Spirit Education Trust* in Hong Kong, the Level 1 around HKD\$1600 to \$2000, Level 2 around HKD\$5700 to \$9000, Level 3 around HKD\$9800 to \$13800. Most students couldn't afford it, the total amount of completion like such training need minimum HKD\$17500.

However, government have funding to support the *ICI*" Higher Diploma in Wine and Beverage Business Management, it includes the *WSET Level 1 to 3* (VTC, 2018). Also, the public Sommelier Competition just began on 6th September 2017. It is the first Young Sommelier Competition and application for public in Hong Kong (RBHK, 2017). And the top certification 'Master of Wine' and 'Master of Sommelier' affect most people want to become a sommelier and try to get the best honour for the reputation (Lee, 2016).

Overall, there have pros and cons, such as government support etc. factors are the benefit for sommelier attractiveness, and the expensive wine course etc. factors are the negative impact.

Table 5: Wine and Spirit Education Trust

(Sources: AWSEC, HKSBTC, HKU-Space and Hong Kong Wine School, 2018)

Criteria of Student Choose Sommelier

Most hospitality schools provide a lot of training and internship, the long working hour, rushing operating and work instability let student feels weary and abandonment especially F&B industry, the student chooses hospitality programme due to interest, certification, and some of them feel hospitality sounds professional before studying the programme (Barron, 2008). However, developing the talent to be a manager or managerial aspect and develop the career in the hospitality industry, the patience is necessary, but most younger generation didn't have it (Littlejohn and Watson, 2004). Overall, the student who has patience and hard work is more accessible to accept and work in the hospitality industry and working continuously. However, the sommelier is the high requirement job, most sommeliers need to learn enormous knowledge like region, grape varieties, winemaking process, viniculture, topography, soil etc., those professional and complex information let many people couldn't accept, and the work instability affect the people participate sommelier job (Giorgione, 2016). Moreover, the alcohol is the most critical factor that people purchase the wine, but that

will have an alternative drink like sake, beer, spirit etc. drinks (Pettigrew and Charters, 2010). How to let people appreciate the wine and choose the restaurant house wine is the essential factor that wine steward or sommelier facing, it also affects student's career intention to be the sommelier.

In recent years, the wine sales in China increased ten times, since 2008 'China Reduction in Tax Barriers', it let China frenzy of organising numerous competitions for aspiring sommeliers and letting many younger generation links with sommelier job (Krich, 2018). Although some hospitality graduates never join or return to the industry, some of them have a strong passion for hospitality, the passionate and comprehensive training can motivate the young generation continuous staying in this industry, and the youth who try to learn and keep more communication with customer, that can let them easy to accept the job which is long working hours and rush like F&B in hospitality industry (Brown et al., 2015).

Prospect of Sommelier

Generally, the customer may select the wine in the restaurant depending on wine menu, it is less communicated with wine captain and sommelier, so wine server maybe zero value (Durham, Pardoe, and Esteban, 2004). However, another stated UK is not appropriate the wine service, but French pursued wine service and had a demand, so they need the sommelier due to different country has their unique wine culture (Cohen, d'Hauteville, and Sirieix, 2009). Furthermore, China needs sommelier talent to fulfil the high standard service needs due to the most Chinese they lack knowledge and concept of food matching, serving, and storage of wine (Jenster and Cheng, 2008). Also, the Chinese winemaking was also developed and matured too late due to war before 1949 although winemaking ⁵⁹ in China dates back more than 2000 years ago, the culture is difference (Jenster and Cheng, 2008).

Finally, the sommelier needs to concern the knowledge of wine's brand, because the wine label and package design also attract the consumer select the wine, but they don't know the wine quality (Boudreaux and Palmer, 2007). In fact, the consumer chooses the wine based on the unilateral label information like brand, and it doesn't mean the consumer recognise that is a quality wine (Cohen, 2009). However, Atkin, Nowak and Garcia (2007) stated that the consumer recognise the price, quality, and value, those are measured to be crucial determinants of product choice to affect the consumer.

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3 Methodology

The purpose of this research aims to realize hospitality graduating students' intentions of developing their future career as sommeliers based on the growing Asian wine market.

This chapter would analyse the pros and cons of the primary research and secondary research in this study. For examining appropriateness and effectiveness, the analysis will focus on the primary research. Moreover, this chapter also describes research design, sampling, data collection and analysis.

3.1 Research Design

This research classified primary and secondary. DeVault (2018, para. 2) stated that "Primary research is designed to meet your unique and specific needs". For secondary research, Fatteross (2018, para. 4) stated that "Secondary research is a type of research has already been compiled, gathered, organised and published by others". Compare with primary research, secondary research can provide the general information, and the primary research is further studying the issues and identify validly or not (DeVault, 2018).

In this paper, it will use a lot of journals, websites and the newspapers especially using the secondary research on the literature review and discussion. For the primary research, questionnaire is the main primary research tool and it would be used for collecting the data. Compare with interview, the interview is related to qualitative research, which required much more time to invite interviewee and conduct the analysis. The questionnaire will be easier to invite the student, no matter the student is hospitality diploma, higher diploma or degree program, they can easy to finish the survey rather than use a lot of time to prepare the interview.

3.2 Sampling

The target sample focused on the hospitality student that request the student who must be studying the hospitality certificate course, diploma programme or bachelor's degree.

Moreover, all samples would limit age, only nine samplings were around 24 years old. If higher than 25 years old, the higher education and long working experience may affect the project result, not the purpose of this paper.

3.3 Questionnaire Design

For this research, it is mainly focused on hospitality student, no other subject or post-graduate. Except for the age and education level, the personal information also requests the student to fill the gender. Besides, the questionnaire would be designed for English and Chinese bi-lingual version, it had shown in the appendix.

The quantitative method would be used, the questionnaire is the paper survey and it designed three parts. Part A is related the student's intention to develop future career as a sommelier and understanding of sommelier. Part B refers to the essential attributes affecting hospitality graduating students' career intentions and Part C refers to the students' major concerns for developing future career as a sommelier factors. All questions will refer to the objectives.

The part A used yes and no question because it mainly consists of statements about the job content of a sommelier to test students' understanding, when the student got a right answer with six questions above which means that student is better 'Understanding'. Through the data, that can analyse and study the image and job content of sommelier that is the student expected.

Part B and C both used four point Likert scale because it is no neutral option compare with five or seven point Likert scale, the neutral choice would affect the sample answer the question when they were pondering (Vagias and Wade, 2006). Part B and C both questions contained working hours, salary, promotional prospects, interest, bonus, work life balance and job content. In the four point Likert scale of the questionnaire, 1 is strongly disagree and 4 is strongly agree. Through the data, that can analyse and study the graduating students' career intentions and their concerns.

Moreover, the final part is personal information because sensitive information to be put last.

All the data will use Excel to analysis. Moreover, it will study the part A is it influence the answer of part C while the student understands the job content of sommelier or not, it will explain on finding.

3.4 Data Collection

Total 114 questionnaires were face-to-face self-administered, and four questionnaires were sent out by social media because four samples came from other regions which are the famous hospitality school like Swiss Hotel Management School 'SHMS'. The diverse hospitality student can let the study more comprehensive.

The data collection started from 18th March to 28th March, total eleven days. All questionnaires had a code and marked the submission day for identification.

In 114 questionnaires, the data mainly collected in ² Institute of Vocational Education (IVE) Haking Wong campus and Institute of Vocational Education (IVE) Chai Wan campus. The four questionnaires were collected on social media.

4 Findings and Discussion

Total 118 completed questionnaire were received and valid, including four questionnaires were received from overseas institutes via social media, with a 100 per cent response rate. The remaining 114 completed questionnaire were received from respondents who are studying hospitality programmes at local institutes, including Institute of Vocational Education (IVE) Haking Wong and Chai Wan campus.

4.1 Demographic Characteristic of Respondents

According to the demographic characteristic of the respondents that showed in Table 6, it found that 118 respondents, (58.5%) were male and (41.5%) were female. Almost 60% (67 respondents) were aged between 18 and 20 years old. Then, almost 40% (40 respondents) were aged between 21 to 23 years old. Moreover, over half of the respondents (66.1%) were the sub-degree or higher diploma level, the other respondents studying bachelor degree level.

To sum up, these survey majority respondents were male, 18 to 20 years old and studying the higher diploma.

Table 6: Demographic Characteristic of Respondents (N=118)

Demographic Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	69	58.5%
Female	49	41.5%
Age		
Under 18	2	1.7%
18 - 20	67	56.8%
21 - 23	40	33.9%
24 or above	9	7.6%
Education		
Sub-degree or Higher Diploma	78	66.1%
Bachelor Degree	40	33.9%

4.2 Respondent's Perception to the Sommelier Job Content and Deviation

According to the respondent's perception to the sommelier job content that showed in Table 6, it showed almost 80% (94) of respondents had a good understanding of the job contents of sommelier, the understanding rate is high.

The Table 7 showed that the top three sommelier's key responsibilities as a respondent's perception include 'Providing food and wine pairing according to guest's budget and preference', 'Designing and update the wine list' and 'Cooperating with chefs for the daily special or wine paring suggestions'.

The respondents who understood sommelier's key responsibilities had chosen the 'Providing food and wine pairing' was top one (96.8%), 'Design and update the wine list' and 'Cooperating with chefs' were the top two (95.7%). Oppositely, the respondent who was not understanding sommelier's key responsibilities had chosen the 'Cooperating with chefs' to be a top one (91.7%), the top two and three were under 90%.

Overall, most respondents just knew the shape of sommelier, they didn't know the detail of sommelier's job content such as 'Organising Wine Tasting Events' and 'Providing Wine Training'. The sommelier education needs to improve more.

Table 7: Respondent's perception to the sommelier job content

	<u>Understanding</u> <u>(79.66%)</u>	<u>Not Understanding</u> <u>(20.34%)</u>
Questionnaire <i>Part A</i> (Understanding of job content as a sommelier)		
<i>Total: (N=118)</i>	<i>(N=94)</i>	<i>(N=24)</i>
Q1: (Organise wine tasting events)	72.3%	25.0%
Q2: (Maintain Beverage Cost and Inventory within the Budget)	86.2%	37.5%
Q3: (Cooperate with Chefs for the daily special or wine paring suggestions)	95.7%	91.7%
Q4: (Design and Update the Wine List)	95.7%	75.0%
Q5: (Provide Training for Staff to Improve their Wine Knowledge)	80.9%	41.7%
Q6: (Promote and Upsell Wine and other Alcoholic Beverages)	87.2%	54.2%
Q7: (Ensure all Beverage Equipment is clean and in Good Condition)	92.6%	50.0%
Q8: (Provide Food and Wine Pairing According to Guest's Budget and Preference)	96.8%	83.3%

4.3 Summary of Key Attributes Affecting Hospitality Graduating Students' Career Intentions

According to Table 8, compare with the 'Mean', it is shown that the students' job hunting mainly focus on 'Interest', second is 'Job Content' and the third is 'Promotion Prospects'.

To sum up, the hospitality graduating students would base on 'Interest', 'Job Content' and 'Promotion Prospects' to select their future career job. The comparison of this result and other kinds of literature, which will show on discussion part.

Table 8: Key Attributes Affecting Hospitality Graduating Students' Career Intentions

4.4 Summary of Students' Major Concerns for Developing Future Career as a Sommelier Factors

According to Table 9, compare with the 'Mean', the top one and two were 'Interest' and 'Job Content', same to part B. And the top three was 'Salary'.

To sum up, the hospitality graduating students would base on 'Interest', 'Job Content' and 'Salary' to select sommelier. The result was difference with part B such as 'Salary', it shown student expected sommelier's salary was higher than another job, but the sommelier's promotion prospects were not well. The industry needs to enhance sommelier reputation, that will suggest on the recommendation part.

Table 9: Students' Major Concerns for Developing Future Career as a Sommelier Factors

4.5 The Connection between Respondent's Perception and the Students' Major Concerns for Developing Future Career as a Sommelier Factors

Study the significant difference or not of 'Mean' value between respondent's perception and the students' major concerns for developing future career as a sommelier factors is very important. It is because the respondent's perception to the sommelier job content would affect the respondent feeling, if the respondent didn't know what sommelier is, it would affect the survey of hospitality graduating students' intention to be a sommelier.

To find the significant difference, it would like to use the t-test to examine the significant difference between two sets of data, which can easy to compare the difference between the respondent who had more or less understanding of the sommelier's job contents.

It couldn't use the 'Mean' to analyse the data deeply especially data significant or not. It is because these two difference groups were independent, the respondents of two groups were also difference. If compare these two data with the 'Mean', it is not fair. So, T-test is very suitable for this case.

The T-test which based on 95% confidence level, the two-tailed analysis would be used, it checked the $P(T \leq t)$ and analysed is it need to reject or accept H_0 (Null Hypothesis). The two-tailed t test should be fulfilled ($p < 0.025$) to prove the data is significant between two group. It is focused on "Is group "Understanding" agree (Q1 to Q7 one of them) is more important to be a Sommelier than group "Non-Understanding".

After the analysis, no question is significant ($p < 0.025$) and no question rejected H_0 (Null Hypothesis). Thus, the group 'Understanding' and group 'Non-Understanding' were no different.

On the other words, the graduating student would not base on understanding sommelier's key responsibilities or not to affect them to choose sommelier as a future career job. No matter interest, job content and salary are the main factors which affect the hospitality graduating students' intention to be a sommelier, the group 'Understanding' and 'Non-Understanding' were no significant difference of 'Mean' value.

Table 10: Two-Sample *t* Test Results ^a

Hypothesis: Is group "Understanding" agree (Q1 to Q7 one of them) is more important to be a Sommelier than group "Non-Understanding"? ($H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$; $H_a: \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$)

Item	Mean (Understanding ^b / Non-Understanding ^c)	df	t Stat	P(T<=t) two-tail (p<0.025)
Question 1 (Working Hours)	2.55 ^b / 2.58 ^c	116	-0.18	0.86
Question 2 (Salary)	2.73 ^b / 2.88 ^c	116	-0.77	0.44
Question 3 (Promotion Prospects)	2.67 ^b / 2.67 ^c	116	0.02	0.98
Question 4 (Interest)	2.94 ^b / 2.83 ^c	116	0.57	0.57
Question 5 (Bonus)	2.70 ^b / 2.58 ^c	116	0.78	0.44
Question 6 (Work Life Balance)	2.78 ^b / 2.58 ^c	116	1.17	0.24
Question 7 (Job Content)	2.98 ^b / 2.63 ^c	116	2.23	0.027

^aShowing those items found to be significantly different.

^bTotal sample size = 94.

^cTotal sample size = 24.

4.6 Analysing the Factor of Student's Intention to Develop Future Career as a Sommelier

This part has analysed the respondent who wanted to develop the career as a sommelier or not while they possessed different levels of understanding of the sommelier's key responsibilities. According to the Table 11, 'Understanding' almost 30% (28 respondents) wanted to be a sommelier and 'Not Understanding' almost 20% (5 respondents) wanted to be a sommelier. Overall, roughly 30% (33 respondents) wanted to be a sommelier.

After the result of *t* test which was almost 0.39, higher than 0.025 a lot, it showed the data between 'Understanding' and 'Not Understanding' isn't significant, it couldn't compare two group. But overall almost 30% respondents wanted to be a sommelier, that situation is acceptable.

Additionally, it only had 33 respondents (28%) wanted to be a sommelier, that includes 26 respondents (78.79%) were male, most of them were higher diploma level (66.67%) and almost half of them were 18 to 20 years old (48.48%). On average, for every 20 respondents in this study, five or six of them had indicated their intention to be a sommelier upon graduation. Thus, the sommelier education is necessary which attract younger generation entering profession.

Table 11: Analysing the Factor of Student's Intention to Develop Future Career as a
Sommelier

Upon graduation, they would like to develop their career as a sommelier			
	Understanding (N=94)	Not Understanding (N=24)	Overall (N=118)
Want to be Sommelier	28 (29.8%)	5 (20.8%)	33 (28.0%)
Not want to be Sommelier	66 (70.2%)	19 (79.2%)	85 (72.0%)
P(T<=t) two-tail		0.38737241	

4.7 Findings Overview

Overall, affecting the hospitality graduating students' intention to be a sommelier is based on interest, job content and salary.

The wine business growing is the recent factor, most people drink wine due to the food and wine pairing and attracted by flavour variance, the sommelier had a market especially bar (Zanten and Rob, 2005). However, it is less affect hospitality graduating students' intention to be a sommelier, because of two points.

First, per five hospitality students had one didn't understand sommelier's critical responsibilities although there was no significant difference between two groups of 'Mean'. Second, only 28% of respondents want to be a sommelier, which means per 10 students only 2 or 3 students want to be a sommelier. Overall situation is deterioration.

Generally, except interest and job content, the student would base on promotion prospects to choose the job (Part B). However, the student based on salary to select sommelier (Part C). They think sommelier is higher salary job but the promotion prospects are limited, which is difference with Part B result.

Thus, the sommelier education needs to improve, and the situation of hospitality graduating students' intention to be a sommelier is not well. All the suggestion will explain in recommendation part.

4.8 Discussions

In finding, the result found out the main factors affecting the hospitality graduating students' intention to be a sommelier is 'Interest', 'Job content' and 'Salary'. But most hospitality graduating students would base on 'Interest', 'Job Content' and 'Promotion Prospects' to select their future career job.

In the Australian hospitality graduating student attitudes and values study, the 'Promotion Opportunities', 'Salary' and the 'Colleague Relationship' are principal factors affecting the hospitality graduating students choose their future job (Richardson, 2008). However, the 'Interesting' is very important too, 'Interest' would affect the student continue to work this job and give patients, most hospitality graduating student interest that job is related their experience such as internship (Jenkins, 2001). And the working hour is the main item which affects the hospitality graduates fear to work in the industry (Schoffstall, 2013).

Compare this result and the finding, 'Promotion Prospects' is related to 'Promotion Opportunities', but there hadn't mentioned 'Job content', it mention the influence of 'Colleague Relationship'. Undeniably, 'Colleague Relationship' is very important especially the relationship with manager or another managerial role. Unfortunately, this item didn't mention in the questionnaire because we never know the manager before you work in there. Thus, 'Colleague Relationship' and 'Job content' didn't have any conflict.

In fact, the sommelier is the professional job which is high wage (Giorgione, 2016).

However, Australia had many hospitality graduates are contemplating other industry, and most of them ¹⁸ with work experience in the hospitality industry, 43.6% of them will not work in the hospitality industry after graduation. (Richardson, 2008).

5 Recommendations

For the recommendation, based on above information and analysis, the suggestion would show below.

5.1 Enhancing the Training of Sommelier Education

First, it is recommended to enhance the training of sommelier and wine education, let more student understand sommelier's job content and relevant responsibility. Although the graduating student would not base on understanding sommelier's key responsibilities or not to affect them to choose sommelier as a future career job, the sommelier education is necessary. After the data analysis, it was found that almost 30% students who had more understanding of sommelier's key responsibilities, they would prefer to develop the career as a sommelier.

In addition, most students didn't know some specific sommelier's job content like 'Organising Wine Tasting Events', the perception of sommelier's key responsibilities was limited and less. Thus, the sommelier education is necessary.

5.2 Encourage More Sommelier Study

Second, it is recommended to encourage the industry to study more about sommelier. Nowadays, except the journal of understanding the sommelier effect, the sommelier study or related study was insufficient. Also, it hadn't enough data to analyse the sommelier job situation like the 'VTC Publications 2015 Catering Industry Manpower Survey Report' just analyse the catering beverage job situation and the Hong Kong Sommelier Association didn't have any report for the sommelier job situation. The 'Sommelier' term like the mysterious job.

5.3 Enhancing Sommelier Popularity

Third, it is recommended to enhance sommelier popularity and reputation, let the sommelier be the restaurant icon or image. In fact, most guest just thinks the sommelier same as the server like waiter although it is wine specialist (Durham et al., 2004). Thus, enhance the sommelier image is very important, most firm especially restaurant hopes to join the competition to let the sommelier be the restaurant image. For example, the Bellavita Best UK Sommelier 2017, the winner 'Valentin Radosav' has captured the sommelier thriving, competitive industry by Sharing his expert skill and knowledge." (UK Sommelier Association, 2017). He became the star in the UK and his restaurant.

After the data analysis, the hospitality graduating students would base on 'Interest', 'Job Content' and 'Promotion Prospects' to select their expected job. However, except 'Interest' and 'Job Content', they didn't base on 'Promotion Prospects' to select sommelier job, they just based on 'Salary'. It has shown student expected sommelier's salary was higher than another job, but the sommelier's promotion prospects were not well.

In fact, every 20 respondents in this study, only five or six of them had indicated their intention to be a sommelier upon graduation. Thus, the industry need to enhance sommelier popularity and reputation, let younger generation expect sommelier is high salary job and abundant promotion prospects.

6 Conclusion

To sum up, the sommelier is the important role of design and provide the best wine list and sales. Those factors are significant to the restaurant, which will affect the whole business profit and image (Wile and Julius, 1975). However, the high market demand of sommelier didn't attract the student's career intention. According to Table 8 and 9, most students just based on job content and interest to choose the job, it is also suitable to apply in the sommelier aspect, but the result (Table 11) shown that every 10 students only 2 or 3 students want to be a sommelier and the Table 7 demonstrated that the massive difference between understanding and non-understanding.

7 Limitation of Study

There has limitation of this report. First is the research just focuses on Asia-Pacific regions, it is not representing the globally. But the study of the global hospitality students who intend to the sommelier are vast, it can't study all of it, the present paper just focuses on Asia Pacific, China, and Hong Kong, the findings were not representative.

Second is the sampling had limitation. The Asia-Pacific members also include People's Republic of China, Macau, Korea, Japan, Indonesia, Vietnam, Singapore etc. regions or countries (APEC, 2017). However, the survey just focusses on the Hong Kong local students, only three sampling were Taiwan, one sampling from Switzerland.

The third is the sampling difficult to represent Hong Kong situation. Because the most sampling was coming from Vocational Training Council 'VTC' students especially the 'VTC' sub-organisation like ⁴² Hong Kong Institute of Vocational Education 'IVE' students and School for Higher and Professional Education 'SHAPE' students. Only two Hong Kong Polytechnic University sampling and two of The ⁴² School of Professional Education and Executive Development 'SPEED' sampling. That means the survey was not representative.

In addition, this study just focuses on hospitality graduating students' intention to be a sommelier, it has not studied how long the student work for a sommelier and non hospitality graduating students' intention. The study was not representative.

8 Future Research

⁷⁰ This paper provided basic information as applied to the student's job intention especially sommelier. In the future, I recommend studying the important factors of how the sommelier affect the restaurant's business and the future sommelier trend, which will complement the ⁴ Manske and Cordua (2005). The journal of understanding the sommelier effect. Also, I recommend studying the elimination of wine duty improves wine sales in the restaurant industry.

4

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Appendix

Appendix A: Questionnaire

Does the Recent Growth of Wine Business Affect Hospitality Graduating Students' Intention to be a Sommelier?

Questionnaire

I am Calvin, a student of Sheffield Hallam University and currently studying the Bachelor of Science (Hons) in International Hospitality Business Management. I am now conducting a survey to examine hospitality graduating students' intention to develop the career as a Sommelier based on the recent growth of the wine market in Asia. Your participation in this survey is voluntary. Collected data will only be used for this study and will be treated as confidential.

我是英國謝菲爾德哈蘭大學學生。本問卷目的是為了研究酒店及款代學生的就業意向，並基於亞洲葡萄酒市場的發展，進一步研究侍酒師（品酒師）行業的吸引力和推動力。通過這項研究，可能會對學院或葡萄酒市場提供有利資料。故此，是次問卷調查十分重要，期望參與者謹慎作答。

Part A: Understanding of job content as a Sommelier.

(Please put X in the appropriate box) (請把 X 放在適當的方框內)

I think a Sommelier's key responsibilities includes...

(我認為侍酒師的主要職責包括...)

Y - Yes (是) N - No (否)

	Y	N
1. to organize wine tasting events. 籌辦品酒活動。		
2. to maintain beverage cost and inventory within the budget. 在預算內維持飲料成本及庫存		
3. to cooperate with chefs for the daily special or wine paring suggestions. 與廚師合作，給予日常葡萄酒與食物搭配的建議		
4. to design and update the wine list. 設計和更新酒單		
5. to provide training for staff to improve their wine knowledge. 提供內部員工培訓，提高他們葡萄酒的知識。		
6. to promote and upsell wine and other alcoholic beverages. 促銷及推擴葡萄酒或其他酒類飲料。		
7. to ensure all beverage equipment is clean and in good condition. 確保所有飲料設備清潔且狀況良好。		
8. to provide food and wine pairing according to guest's budget and preference. 根據客人的預算及喜好提供相應的葡萄酒，並配對美食。		

Part B: Key factors affecting hospitality graduating students' career intention.

³
SD- Strongly Disagree **D- Disagree** **A- Agree** **SA- Strongly Agree**
 SD - 非常不同意 D - 不同意 A - 同意 SA - 非常同意

Upon completion of my current study, I will...

(完成學業後，我會...)

	SD	D	A	SA
1. choose the career based on its working hours. 根據工作時間而選擇職業				
2. choose the career based on its salary. 根據薪酬而選擇職業。				
3. choose the career based on its promotion prospects. 根據晉升前景而選擇職業。				
4. choose the career based on my interest. 根據興趣而選擇職業。				
5. choose the career based on its bonus or employment benefits. 根據就業福利或獎金而選擇職業。				
6. choose the career based on work life balance. 根據生活與工作的平衡而選擇職業。				
7. choose the career based on the job content. 根據工作內容而選擇職業。				

Part C: Key factors affecting hospitality graduating students' intention to be a Sommelier.

¹⁵
SD- Strongly Disagree **D- Disagree** **A- Agree** **SA- Strongly Agree**
 SD - 非常不同意 D - 不同意 A - 同意 SA - 非常同意

Upon completion of my current study, if I would like to be a Sommelier...

(完成學業後，如果我成為侍酒師...)

	SD	D	A	SA
1. it is because of its working hours. 是因為工作時間。				
2. it is because of its salary. 是因為薪酬。				
3. it is because of its promotion prospects. 是因為晉升前景。				
4. it is because of my interest. 是因為興趣。				
5. it is because of its bonus or employment benefits. 是因為就業福利或獎金。				
6. it is because of work life balance. 是因為生活與工作的平衡。				
7. it is because of its job content. 是因為工作內容。				

Yes No

Upon graduation, I would like to develop my career as a Sommelier 畢業後，我想成為侍酒師。

Part D: Personal Information (All responses keep confidential.) / 個人資料 (一切保密)

1. Gender (性別):

A) Male (男)

B) Female (女)

2. What is your age group? (年齡)

A) Under 18 (18 歲以下)

B) 18 - 20

C) 21 - 23

D) 24 or above (24 歲以上)

3. Education: ²⁷ Diploma or certificate course ²⁷ Sub-degree or High Diploma Bachelor Degree

教育程度: 文憑或證書課程

副學士或高級文憑

學士學位

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